

Comparitive Study Of Ocimum Sanctum By Supercritical Carbon Dioxide Method And Microwave Assistance Method With Their Pharmacognostic Acitivities.

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ABSTRACT -

Two significant therapeutic plants from the genus *Ocimum*, *Ocimum basilicum* and *Ocimum sanctum*, have been compared in this study using a variety of phytochemical criteria. Investigations have been conducted on the effects of extraction methods, supercritical carbon dioxide method and microwave assistance method. These analyses are essential for choosing plant leaves based on their composition for the production of herbal medications that can be used for a number of conditions, including diabetes, pharmacological activities, respiratory diseases, etc. The results show that these leaves have the potential to be used in nanotechnology, phytomedicine, and extremely nutritious feed.

Given the plant's numerous pharmacological applications across the globe, they are relevant to nutrition, medicine, and veterinary care.

In microwave-assisted hydrodistillation (MHD), the effects of radiation duration and microwave supplied power on the yield and makeup of the essential oil extracted from *Ocimum sanctum*. Microwave-delivered power of 1000 W for 3 minutes of microwave radiation and microwave-delivered power of 300 W for 1 hour of microwave radiation at a

spice to water ratio of 1:20 were the ideal circumstances for MHD. A polyherbal mixture of powdered cardamom seeds, bay leaves, and tulsi leaves was extracted using supercritical carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂). The highest extract yield and maximum antioxidant potency were achieved using a 20 g powdered mixture of tulsi leaf prepared in an adjusted 1:1:2 ratio. bay leaf: tiny cardamom seed extracted at 608°C, 300 bar, and 90 minutes with a gaseous CO₂ flow rate of 2.5 L/min.

KEYWORD: *Ocimum sanctum*, supercritical carbon dioxide extraction, microwave-assisted hydrodistillation, , pharmacological activities,

INTRODUCTION:

A little plant found all over India, *Ocimum sanctum* L. (Family Lamiaceae) is also referred to as holy basil in the West and tulsi in India [1]. The medicinal plant *Ocimum sanctum* L. (family Lamiaceae) is used in the food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and agricultural industries [2]. The Lamiaceae (Labiatae) family includes the genus *Ocimum*, which is wellknown for its significance in the perfume business. The number of species in the genus has been reported in various ways. There are between 50 and 60 species, according to certain sources [3, 4].

The "Rigveda," which is believed to have been composed between 4500 and 1600 BC, has the oldest reference to the usage of plants for medical purposes in Hindu culture.[5] It has long been used as a pain reliever, as well as a repellent and to treat rheumatism, diarrhea, high fever, convulsions, diabetes, eczema, and piles [6, 7]. In particular, because of the anticipated benefits of the supercritical extraction method, the use of supercritical fluids in the extraction of volatile oils and extracts has grown since 2000. The manufacturing of highvalue plant extracts for the food, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical industries has drawn more attention to these procedures.[8,9]

The volatile oil found in *OS* Linn. leaves is 0.7% and contains roughly 71% eugenol and 20% methyl eugenol. Other phytoconstituents included in the *OS* include UA, carvacrol, caryophyllene, apigenin, luteolin, apigenin-7-O-glucuronide, orientin, and molludistin. [10] Supercritical uid extraction is one of several innovative extraction techniques. [11] Another solvent-free and eco-friendly sample pretreatment method is supercritical fluid extraction. Numerous parameters affecting the yields of basil extract extraction were examined in this study, along with a comparison to traditional extraction methods.

The goal of extraction methods is not just to remove active biocompounds from plant samples. Other techniques have been employed, such as supercritical fluid extraction, which produces extracts and pure compounds by using carbon dioxide (SFE CO₂) as the organic solvent. Numerous benefits come with this method, including a brief exposure period to a low-temperature, non-toxic solvent. Additionally, the productivity and quality of the items produced are high. [12]

Since its beginnings, supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) technology has made significant strides and is now the preferred technique in many food processing sectors. SFE has gained

popularity over the past 20 years as a clean, eco-friendly "green" processing method and, in certain situations, as a substitute for organic solvent-based natural product extraction. Comprehensive evaluations of the latest developments in SFE applications in the fields of food science, natural products, by-product recovery, pharmaceuticals, and environmental sciences have been published [13]. Compared to traditional procedures, SFE removes the oil or desired element from the subject material faster. The important components of supercritical fluid extracts are usually kept in their chemically natural state and are usually sanitized and free of contamination [14,15]. SC-CO₂ extraction has been used both alone and in combination with other major or minor lipid components to extract phytosterols from plant materials and/or for food purposes [16].

Non-thermal phenomena that have been widely referred to as "microwave effects" have been reported by numerous researchers in recent literature. The increased reaction rates of thermosetting resins during microwave curing are an example of the microwave effect [17]. The quantity of symposia devoted to microwave processing of materials in recent years indicates the growing interest in this field. The American Ceramic Society and the Materials Research Society (MRS) have hosted nine symposia on microwave processing materials thus far.[18,19]

In mythology, *Ocimum basilicum* is referred to as the "God of Spices," emphasizing its use in cooking. [20] Additionally, a number of dietary products that support and sustain health contain basil. [21] Although this herb is also well-known for its decorative qualities, its wide range of pharmacological activity primarily make it useful for therapeutic purposes.[22,20]

MATERIALS AND TECHNIQUES:

Plant collection site:

Ocimum sanctum L. was chosen for these experiments based on its ethnobotanical uses; only the aerial parts of the plant leaves and flowers were used. The plants were extracted using fresh plants within the first three days of acquisition, and the rest were dried in an oven (LSIS-B2V/VC111 1900 W, Cejl, Czech Republic) at 40 C for 72 hours and stored in vacuum packages at -18 C.

The flowers and leaves were ground (IKA WERKE-M20, Staufen, Germany) at low temperatures to prevent loss and thermal degradation of secondary metabolites, and the particle size distribution was assessed using a set of standard sieves.

Characterization of tulsi powder:

Using a sieve shaker, the powder samples were filtered through a series of standard sieves (5, 10, 14, 20, 24, and 44 Tyler meshes) to determine the mean particle diameter of the powder. The particle size distributions were then noted [23].

It was found that the average particle diameter (d_p) of tulsi powder was 0.4 mm. AOAC method 930.15 was used to determine the tulsi powder's moisture content [24].

Carbon dioxide extraction of tulsi powder:

According to the procedure, dried tulsi powder was extracted using liquid CO₂ [25].

To keep the pump head at 2°C, it is equipped with a modified pump (Speed MAX P/N 7025) and a refrigerated cooling bath. A 50 ml extraction vessel (SS 316) was filled with 20 g of dried tulsi powder.

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Carbon dioxide Supercritical extraction method:

The concept of supercritical fluid extraction (SFE):

Principle- Supercritical carbon dioxide technology (SC-CO₂) is a promising substitute for the traditional thermal processes that would destroy bioactive compounds in food and medicine. It uses pressure and carbon dioxide to kill microorganisms without compromising nutritional value or organoleptic qualities [26].

Supercritical extraction of carbon dioxide Another effective technique for eugenol extraction from ocimum sactum is supercritical carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂) extraction.[27] In order to extract the volatile oil, a two-stage fractional separation technique was used in a flow apparatus to perform supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) with carbon dioxide (CO₂) and 80 g of basil with a mean particle size of 0.6 mm for 2.5 hours at a flow rate of 1.0 kg/h CO₂, at 313 K and 9.0 MPa [28,29].

In the first separator, separation was carried out at 7.0 MPa and 263 K, mostly collecting waxes. The volatile oil (SFEO) was extracted from a second separation that was carried out at 2.0 MPa and 273 K. Gravimetric analysis was used to determine the amount of volatile oil collected, with a 0.1 mg margin of error. The supplier of purity CO₂ (99.995%) was Air Liquide, located in Lisbon, Portugal.

SFE experiments were conducted in a flow apparatus from Applied Separations, Speed™ SFE, which permits extraction to be carried out at temperatures up to 393.2 K and pressures up to 60.0 MPa, in order to obtain basil extracts at higher pressures due to the limitations of SFE equipment (maximum pressure of 30.0 MPa) [30,31].

The extract was incubated at ambient temperature to eliminate any remaining CO₂. A miscible polar substance, such ethanol, can be added as a modifier to supercritical SC-CO₂ to improve its polarity, even if CO₂ is the recommended extraction solvent (for extracting nonpolar chemicals) [32]. 6 The extracts produced using this method have minimal concentrations of undesirable chemicals because of the selectivity required in the SFE process [33].

Additionally, after depressurization, SC-CO₂ turns gaseous and is easily removed from a flow system.[34] Because it is nontoxic, nonexplosive, affordable, and has the capacity to

dissolve lipophilic materials, supercritical carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂) is a desirable substitute for organic solvents. It is also easily extracted from the finished products. [35, 36, 37]

Fig. 1. Comparison of yield of eugenol obtained by different extraction procedure

Application of Supercritical fluid extraction:

The experimental finding that many gases increase their dissolving power when compressed above a certain point serves as the foundation for the use of SFE.[38] Their findings demonstrate that, particularly when a co-solvent is included, the extracts produced by SC-CO₂ have a strong antioxidant potential against the DPPH (2,2 diphenyl-1picrylhydrazyl) radical. Because it enables the extraction of thermally labile or readily oxidized chemicals, SF-CO₂ is significant for the food sector and natural compound extractions in this context.[39]

These days, SFE is widely employed in a variety of industrial applications, such as the decaffeination of coffee, the refining of fatty acids, and the extraction of flavors and essential oils from natural sources that may find use in functional foods and nutraceuticals.[40]

Gases	Critical Temperature (K)	Critical Pressure (MPa)
Carbon dioxide	304.17	7.38
Ethane	305.34	4.87
Methane	190.55	4.59
Ethylene	282.35	5.04
Propane	369.85	4.24

Table 2. Examples of substances used as supercritical solvents and its corresponding critical temperature and pressure. [41]

Microwave Assitance Method:

The Federal Communications Commission (FCC) has designated two frequencies for industrial, scientific, and medical (ISM) uses, which are frequently utilized for microwave heating. The two frequencies that are most frequently utilized are 2.45 GHz and 0.915 GHz. For material processing, microwave furnaces with tunable frequencies between 0.9 and 18 GHz have recently been created [42]. Essential oils can be extracted from plant sources with significant potential using the MAE process.[43].

In a conical flask, around 3g of sample and 200 ml of solvent were combined, and the mixture was microwaved at 700 W for 5 minutes with a 2-minute intermission. Each suspension was pre-leached for ten minutes prior to microwave irradiation. With a duration of 5 minutes for irradiation and 2 minutes for cooling, the microwave irradiation was carried out intermittently, or irradiation-cooling-irradiation. The extraction was done after the sample was treated for five minutes at 700 W in a microwave. Similar procedures to the traditional solvent extraction method were followed for the other steps, such as filtration, concentration, and storage [44].

Because bio-oil contains 15–30 weight percent water and 35–50 weight percent oxygen, it has a poor heating value of 16–18 Mj/kg; also, its high acidity (pH 2-3) adds to its unfavorable characteristics.[45]. Carbon compounds, which are good microwave absorbents with a high ability to absorb and convert microwave energy into heat, have been used in conjunction with microwave heating.[46,47]

Fig.2. Effect of delivered power and time on oil yield under the MHD conditions

Spice to water ratio: 1:20; microwave conditions: 1000 W of power for three minutes, followed by 300 W of power for one hour.[48].

According to the findings, both methods produced different amounts of oil, but the resulting oil profiles were comparable. Eugenol and methyleugenol, which are the same in other articles, are the primary constituents of essential oils.[49, 50,51]

Microwave-Assisted Simultaneous Distillation and Extraction (MA-SDE) Process:

The MA-SDE apparatus was made up of a modified Likens-Nickerson apparatus for simultaneous distillation-extraction (SDE) and a microwave assisted extraction system that served as the heat source [52].The laboratory modified a home microwave oven (Electrolux, Bangkok, Thailand). The highest The power source was 2450 MHz, and 700 W of power was employed. The microwave oven's internal cavity had measurements of 44.0 × 35.5 × 2.59 cm. In the lab, an oven (Electrolux, Bangkok, Thailand) was modified.

The power source was 2450 MHz, and the maximum power used was 700 W. The microwave oven's internal cavity measured 44.0 × 35.5 x 2.59 cm. The process used for SDE was comparable to that described for MA-SDE. Nonetheless, the process used for SDE was comparable to that described for MA-SDE. However, according to earlier study, the operation was conducted for four hours using an electromantle (Mtops, Seoul, Korea, 500 W) as the heating source [53].

Optimization of MAE based on RSM-BBD

Standard order	Microwave power,X1(W)	Solvent to feed ratio, X2(ml/g)	Extraction time,X3(min)	Total extraction yields ,Y(mg/g)
1	100	30	15	6.38
2	200	30	15	6.47
3	100	70	15	6.99
4	200	70	15	7.07
5	100	50	10	6.17
6	200	50	10	6.70
7	100	50	20	6.62

Table-2 Total extraction yield [54]

Microwave applicators and processing systems:

Single mode-

Because of this, single mode applicators are around one wavelength in size, and these cavities need a microwave source with little frequency output fluctuation to sustain the resonant mode. Single mode applicators feature non-uniform but predictable electromagnetic field distributions, and the regions of high and low electromagnetic field are known due to the ability to determine the electromagnetic field using analytical or numerical techniques.

Single mode cavities typically have a single "hot spot" with a high microwave field strength. There are several clear benefits to being able to design an applicator with known high and low field strength regions. Single mode applicators can be used to concentrate the microwave field at a specific spot with the right design. Ceramics have been joined using this technique [55,56].

The single mode cavity provides a highly regulated setting for cure kinetic investigations, allowing for the best possible coupling between the tiny samples. modest samples utilized for kinetic studies do not constitute a significant coupling load in larger microwave cavities, and controlling the process for modest coupling loads is more

challenging. Monitoring the dielectric characteristics while processing is another benefit of single mode cavities.[57]

Multi-mode applicators:

Multi-mode cavities are applicators that have the capacity to support multiple high order modes simultaneously. Microwave ovens at home utilize this kind of applicator. Multimode applicators are frequently built by trial and error, experience, and intuition, in contrast to single mode applicators, which are designed using solutions of the electromagnetic field equations for a certain applicator geometry [58].

The majority of uniformity-creation methods rely on altering the microwave cavity's electromagnetic field. Hybrid heating is another technique created to provide more consistent heating. Combining microwave heating with traditional heat transfer methods like convection, conduction, or radiation can result in hybrid heating. Researchers at Oak Ridge National Laboratory have successfully employed variations of this technique [59].

Pharmacognostic Activities of Ocimum Santum:

1. Analgesic activity

When tested in Swiss mice using the tail immersion technique, the methanolic extract of *O. basilicum* was found to have analgesic efficacy. At a concentration of 200 mg/kg, the extract clearly demonstrated a nociceptive impact in comparison to aspirin and the usual medication.[60]

At a dose of 50 mg/kg body weight, the essential oil increased the latency of pain in the hot plate test. The induction of inhibition of cyclo-oxygenase activity and subsequent inhibition of the biosynthesis of pain mediators such as prostaglandin, prostacyclin, and opioid receptor interactions may be the cause of *O. basilicum*'s obvious analgesic effects.[61]

2. Anti-bacterial activity :

The extract of *O. basilicum* exhibits potential antibacterial action against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, in contrast to several antibacterial agents. [62,63] *O. basilicum* essential oil was found to be bactericidal against Gram-negative bacteria including *Proteus vulgaris*, *P. mirabilis*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*; and Gram-positive bacteria including *Bacillus subtilis*, *Micrococcus flavus*, *M. luteus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, and *Streptococcus faecalis*. [64] Additionally, the plant's aerial portions shown strong antibacterial properties against *Salmonella sp.*, *Escherichia coli*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, and *Clostridium perfringens*. Furthermore, the volatile oil that was isolated from the plant's aerial parts shown a considerable vulnerability to drug-resistant strains of *Enterococcus*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Staphylococcus*. [65,66]

3. Anti-viral activity:

Eugenol is a powerful natural substance that is being studied extensively to determine its biological activity and potential for use as an antibacterial. Additionally, eugenol and acyclovir work in concert to inhibit the herpes virus in vitro; when used alone, eugenol topical application was shown to slow the progression of herpes virus-induced keratitis in mice models. [67] Eugenol demonstrated virucidal activity against the HSV 1 and HSV 2 viruses, ovicidal activity against the parasite *Haemonchus contortus*, [68] which inhabits the gastrointestinal tract, and antiprotozoal activity against *Leishmania*, [69] a group of diseases that cause a wide range of clinical manifestations [70,71]

4. Anti-fungal activity:

Aspergillus fumigatus, *A. flavus*, *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Botrytis fabae*, *Uromyces fabae*, *Aureobasidium pullulans*, *Trichophyton rubrum*, *Microsporum gypseum*, and *Trichoderma viride* have all been reported to be susceptible to the strong antifungal action of *Ocimum basilicum*. [72, 73] The morphological changes in the fungal

hyphae, such as hyphal swelling, mycelial asymmetry, sunken, curling, deformed, and broken hyphae, demonstrated that the extract impeded mycelium growth, spore germination, and germ tube extension.[74] The suppression of the transformation of yeast to mycelial form is the mechanism of action. [75] At the in vitro level, the hexane fraction and crude ethanolic extract made from the leaves of the *O. basilicum* cultivar Maria Bonita both demonstrated anti-cryptococcal efficacy. But the with a low MIC value, the hexane fraction outperformed the ethanolic extract in terms of outcomes. Through the reduction of ergosterol production and capsule size, the extract generated antifungal action. [76]

5. Antioxidant activity:

By raising the amount of antioxidative defense enzymes and significantly lowering lactate dehydrogenase activity and lipid peroxidation, the *O. basilicum* extract's potent antioxidant activity guards against oxidative stress.[77] The higher stability of extracts suggests that purple basil may be a viable source of stable bioactive components, according to a study done to assess how temperature, light, and copigmentation affect the plant's capacity to scavenge free radicals.[78] This leads to a change in metabolism, which in turn reduces the amount of leaves this plant produces [79,80].

6. Anti-osteoporotic effect :

Basil contains phytoestrogens and flavonoids that stop bone resorption. In postmenopausal women, they also aid in maintaining bone density, which has been shown to have some inhibitory effects on osteoporosis. [81,82] Apigenin, which is found in the volatile oil of *O. basilicum*, has been shown to induce programmed cell death of mature osteoclasts and limit bone resorption in the rabbit's long bone. [83] The presence of phytoestrogen, which increases the activity of osteoblasts through the estrogen receptor or by increasing the synthesis of insulin 1-like growth factor-1 (IG-F), may be linked to the antiosteoporotic action. [82, 84]

7.Hypolipidemic activity:

Ocimum basilicum is very helpful in preventing hyperlipidemia and the cardiovascular diseases that are associated with it because it has been shown to have hypolipidemic effects through the use of specific polar phytoconstituents. In mice with induced hyperlipidemia, an aqueous extract of basil significantly reduced the levels of triglycerides and total cholesterol in the liver and plasma.[85]

8. Antidiabetic activity:

Experimental animals have demonstrated hypoglycemic effects from *O. sanctum* leaves [86], [87], [88], and [89]. Blood sugar levels are lowered by decoction made from different plant parts [90]. The physiological pathways of insulin secretion may be stimulated by components of *O. sanctum* leaf extracts, according to a study [91] on rats. Although *Ocimum*'s antiglycemic qualities have been the subject of numerous investigations, its exact mode of action has not yet been determined [91], [92]. According to a study [93] using tulsi

and neem, diabetic patients benefit more from this combination in terms of decreasing their blood sugar levels.

9. Anti-ulcer activity:

The effectiveness of oral administration of *O. basilicum* whole plant extract in managing gastric and duodenal ulceration was evaluated in a cysteamine induced duodenal ulceration model, which demonstrated that both ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *O. basilicum* decreased the ulcer index and the anti-ulcerogenic effects were due to the decrease in pepsin and acid production, which resulted in the subsequent enhancement of gastric mucosal strength.[94]

Significant activity was created in duodenal ulcers by the plant's aqueous extracts; nevertheless, the aqueous extract's activity outperformed that of the ethanolic extract. [95] Such a clear anti-ulcer effect is primarily caused by chemical components such as 1,8-cineone, methyl eugenol, linalool, eugenol, and anthocyanins. [96] *O. basilicum* essential oil at higher doses (200 and 400 $\mu\text{L}/\text{kg}$) reduced ulcer severity, area, and index.

Myeloperoxidase levels and the total colitis index decreased, indicating that *O. basilicum* has antiulcer properties. [97] Hexane extract from *Ocimum basilicum* was also shown to have antiinflammatory, antioxidant, and anxiolytic properties that help treat stomach ulcers brought on by aspirin. Therefore, *O. basilicum* can be used as a medication or nutritional supplement to stop stomach ulcers brought on by aspirin. In individuals receiving aspirin-based chronic therapy. [98].

10. Anti-inflammatory activity:

In rats with acute (carrageenan-induced pedal oedema) and chronic (croton oil-induced granuloma and exudate development) inflammations, methanolic extract (500 mg/kg) and aqueous suspension of OS demonstrated analgesic, antipyretic, and anti-inflammatory properties [99]. Due to their ability to inhibit the cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase pathways of arachidonic acid metabolism, the fixed oil and linolenic acid exhibit strong antiinflammatory properties against PGE₂, leukotriene, and arachidonic acid-induced paw oedema in rats [100].

References:

1. Mediratta PK, Sharma KK, Singh S. Evaluation of immunomodulatory potential of *Ocimum sanctum* seed oil and its possible mechanism of action. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2002 Apr 1;80(1):15-20.
2. Singh AP. Promising phytochemicals from Indian medicinal plants. *Ethnobotanical leaflets*. 2005;2005(1):18.
3. Wollenweber E, Dörr M. Exudate flavonoids of some Juglandaceae. *Natural Product Communications*. 2009 Feb;4(2):1934578X0900400208.
4. Suchorska, K.; Osinska, E. Variability of the purple and the lettuce-leaved sweet basil (*Ocimum basilicum* L.). *Herba Polonica*, (1992) XXXVIII, 175–181.
5. Joshi Bishnu, Sah Govind Prasad, Basnet Buddha Bahadur, Bhatt Megh Raj, Sharma Dinita, Subedi Krishna, Pandey Janardhan and Mall Rajani, Phytochemical extraction and antimicrobial properties of different medicinal plants: *Ocimum sanctum* (Tulsi), *Eugenia caryophyllata* (Clove), *Achyranthes bidentata* (Datiwan) and *Azadirachta indica* (Neem), *JMA*, 3(1), 1-7 (2011)
6. D. J. Chitwood, "Phytochemical based strategies for nematodes control," *Annual Review of Phytopathology*, vol. 40, pp. 221-249, 2003.
7. F. B. Hotlets, T. Ueda-Nakamura, D. A. G. Cortez, J. A. Morgado-Díaz, and C. V. Nakamura, " Effects of essential oil of *Ocimum gratissimum* on the trypanosomatid *Herpetomonas samuelpessoai*," *Acta Protozoologica*, vol. 42, pp. 269-276, 2003.
8. Reverchon E, Adami R, Campardelli R, Della Porta G, De Marco I, Scognamiglio M. Supercritical fluids based techniques to process pharmaceutical products difficult to micronize: Palmitoylethanolamide. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*. 2015 Jul 1;102:24-31.
9. Knez Ž, Markočič E, Leitgeb M, Primožič M, Hrnčič MK, Škerget M. Industrial applications of supercritical fluids: A review. *Energy*. 2014 Dec 1;77:235-43.
10. Gupta A, Polyak CS, Bishop RD, Sobel J, Mintz ED. Laboratory-confirmed shigellosis in the United States, 1989–2002: epidemiologic trends and patterns. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2004 May 15;38(10):1372-7.
11. Daniels N. *Just health: meeting health needs fairly*. Cambridge University Press; 2007 Oct 22.
12. Pisoschi AM, Pop A, Cimpeanu C, Predoi G. Antioxidant capacity determination in plants and plant-derived products: a review. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity*. 2016;2016(1):9130976.
13. Herrero, M.; Mendiola, J.A.; Cifuentes, A.; Ibáñez, E. Supercritical fluid extraction: Recent advances and application. *J. Chromatogr. A* 2010, 1217, 2495–2511
14. Hultin, H.O. Oxidation of lipids in seafoods. In *Seafoods: Chemistry, Processing Technology and Quality*; Shahidi, F., Botta, J.R., Eds.; Chapman & Hall: London, UK, 1994; pp. 49–74.
15. Staby, A.; Møllerup, J. Separation of constituents of fish oil using supercritical fluids: A review of experimental solubility, extraction, and chromatographic data. *Fluid Phase Equilib.* 1993, 91, 349–386.

16. Laplante S, Souchet N, Bryl P. Comparison of low-temperature processes for oil and coenzyme Q10 extraction from mackerel and herring. *European Journal of Lipid Science and Technology*. 2009 Feb;111(2):135-41.
17. Marand E, Baker HR, Graybeal JD. Comparison of reaction mechanisms of epoxy resins undergoing thermal and microwave cure from in situ measurements of microwave dielectric properties and infrared spectroscopy. *Macromolecules* 1992;25:2243±2252.
18. Sutton WH, Brooks MH, Chabinsky IJ, editors. *Microwave processing of materials*, Materials Research Society Proceedings, Vol. 124, Pittsburgh: Materials Research Society, 1988.
19. Clark DE, Sutton WH, Lewis DA, editors. *Microwaves: theory and application in materials processing IV*, ceramic transactions, Vol. 80, Westerville, OH: American Ceramic Society, 1997.
20. Machado, M. M.; De Oliveira, L. F.; Zuravski, L. *Ocimum Basilicum L. Antiinflammatory Actions and Potential Usage for Arthritic Conditions*. In *Bioactive Food as Dietary Interventions for Arthritis and Related Inflammatory Diseases*; Elsevier: Academic Press, 2019; pp 481–487.
21. Sestili P, Ismail T, Calcabrini C, Guescini M, Catanzaro E, Turrini E, Layla A, Akhtar S, Fimognari C. The Potential Effects of *Ocimum Basilicum* on Health: A Review of Pharmacological and Toxicological Studies. *Expert. Opin. Drug Metab Toxicol*. 2018, 14(7), 679–692.
22. Purushothaman, B.; Srinivasan, P.; Suganthi, R.; Ranganathan, P.; Gimbun, B.; Shanmugam, K. A Comprehensive Review on *Ocimum Basilicum*. *J Nat Remedies*. 2018, 18, 71–85.
23. Bhattacharjee S, Rajaraman P, Jacobs KB, Wheeler WA, Melin BS, Hartge P, Yeager M, Chung CC, Chanock SJ, Chatterjee N. A subset-based approach improves power and interpretation for the combined analysis of genetic association studies of heterogeneous traits. *The American Journal of Human Genetics*. 2012 May 4;90(5):821-35.
24. Sambucetti ME, Zuleta A. Resistant starch in dietary fiber values measured by the AOAC method in different cereals. *Cereal Chemistry*. 1996 Nov 1;73(6):759-61.
25. Clare HA, Adams R, Maher CG. A systematic review of efficacy of McKenzie therapy for spinal pain. *Australian journal of Physiotherapy*. 2004 Jan 1;50(4):209-16.
26. Jimenez-Sanchez, C., Lozano-Sanchez, A. S. G., & Fernandez-Gutierrez, A. (2017) Alternatives to conventional thermal treatments in fruit-juice processing. Part 1: Techniques and applications, *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 57, 501-523.
27. D. Chatterjee and P. Bhattacharjee, Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction of eugenol from clove buds, *Food Bioprocess Technol.*, 2013, 6, 2587–2599.
28. Coelho JA, Grosso C, Pereira AP, Burillo J, Urieta JS, Figueiredo AC, Barroso JG, Mendes RL, Palavra AM. Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction of volatiles from *Satureja fruticosa* Béguinot. *Flavour and fragrance journal*. 2007 Sep;22(5):438-42.
29. Coelho JP, Cristino AF, Matos PG, Rauter AP, Nobre BP, Mendes RL, Barroso JG, Mainar A, Urieta JS, Fareleira JM, Sovová H. Extraction of volatile oil from aromatic plants with supercritical carbon dioxide: experiments and modeling. *Molecules*. 2012 Sep;17(9):10550-73.
30. Coelho JP, Bernotaityte K, Miraldes MA, Mendonça AF, Stateva RP. Solubility of ethanamide and 2-propenamide in supercritical carbon dioxide. Measurements and correlation. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data*. 2009 Sep 10;54(9):2546-9.

- 31.Coelho JP, Mendonça AF, Palavra AF, Stateva RP. On the solubility of three disperse anthraquinone dyes in supercritical carbon dioxide: new experimental data and correlation. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*. 2011 Apr 20;50(8):4618-24.
- 32.Taylor, S. L., Eller, F. J. & King, J. W. (1997) A comparison of oil and fat content in oilseed and ground beef- using supercritical fluid extraction and related analytical techniques, *Food Res Int.*, 30(5), 365-370.
- 33.Sa´nchez-Camargo, A. P., Mendiola, J. A., Iba´n˜ez, E., Herrero, M., in: Reedijk, J. (2014) (Ed). *Reference Module in Chemistry, Molecular Sciences and Chemical Engineering*, Elsevier Inc, Waltham, M. A. pp 1–14.
- 34.Pan, J., Zhang, C., Zhang, Z. & Li, G. (2014) Review of online coupling of sample preparation techniques with liquid chromatography, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 815, 1–15.
- 35.Wang, L. & Weller, C. (2006) Recent advances in extraction of nutraceuticals from plants, *Trends Food Sci Technol*, 17(6), 300–12
- 36.Wang, L., Weller, C., Schlegel, V., Carr, T. & Cuppett, S. (2008) Supercritical CO₂ extraction of lipids from grain sorghum dried distillers grains with solubles. *Bioresour Technol.*, 99(5), 1373–82.
- 37.Cavero S., Garc´ıa-Risco M., Mar´ın F., Jaime L., Santoyo S., Se˜nor´ans F., Reglero G., Iba˜nez E. (2006) Supercritical fluid extraction of antioxidant compounds from oregano: chemical and functional characterization via LC-MS and in vitro assays, *J Supercrit Fluid*, 38(1), 62–9.
- 38.Brunner, G. (2003) Supercritical fluid extraction of ethanol from aqueous solutions, *J. Supercrit. Fluids*, 25(1), 45–55.
- 39.Herrero M, Mendiola J, Cifuentes A, Iba˜nez E. (2010) Supercritical fluid extraction: recent advances and applications, *J. Chromatogr*, (16), 2495–511
- 40.Akinlua, A., Torto, N. & Ajayi, T. R. (2008) Supercritical fluid extraction of aliphatic hydrocarbons from Niger Delta sedimentary rock, *J. Supercrit. Fluids*, 45(1), 57–63
- 41.Rizvi, S.S.H.; Yu, Z.R.; Bhaskar, A.R.; Raj, C.C.B. *Fundamentals of processing with supercritical fluid*. In *Supercritical Fluid Processing of Food and Biomaterials*; Rizvi, S.S.H., Ed.; Chapman and Hall: Glasgow, UK, 1994; pp. 1–26.
- 42.Lauf RJ, Bible DW, Johnson AC, Everliegh CA. 2–18 GHz broadband microwave heating systems. *Microwave Journal* 1993;36(11):24–27.
- 43.Mahfud M, Putri DK, Dewi IE, Kusuma HS. Extraction of essential oil from cananga (*Cananga odorata*) using solvent-free microwave extraction: A preliminary study. *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*. 2017 Jan 1;10(1):86-91.
- 44.Verma SC, Jain CL, Kumari A, Padhi MM, Devalla RB. Microwave-assisted extraction and rapid isolation of ursolic acid from the leaves of *Eucalyptus × hybrida* Maiden and its quantification using HPLC-diode array technique. *J Sep Sci*. 2013;36(7):1255-1262. doi: 10.1002/jssc.201200950
- 45.Duan, P.; Savage, P.E. Upgrading of Crude Algal Bio-Oil in Supercritical Water. *Bioresour. Technol*. 2011, 102 (2), 1899–1906.
- 46.Menéndez, J.A.; Arenillas, A.; Fidalgo, B.; Fernández, Y.; Zubizarreta, L.; Calvo, E.G.; Bermudez, J.M. Microwave Heating Processes Involving Carbon Materials. *Fuel Process. Technol*. 2010, 91, 1–8.

- 47.Salema, A.A.; Ani, F.N. Pyrolysis of Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch Biomass Pellets Using Multimode Microwave Irradiation. *Bioresour. Technol.* 2012, 125, 102–107.
- 48.Zi-Tao Jiang , Xue Feng , Rong Li & Ying Wang (2013) Composition Comparison of Essential Oils Extracted by Classical Hydro distillation and Microwave-assisted Hydrodistillation from *Pimenta dioica* , *Journal of Essential Oil Bearing Plants*, 16:1, 45-50,
- 49.Minott, D.A. and Brown, H.A. (2007). Differentiation of fruiting and non-fruiting *Pimenta dioica*(L.) merr trees based on composition of leaf volatiles. *J. Essent. Oil Res.*, 19: 354-357.
- 50.Padmakumari, K.P., Sasidharan, I. and Sreekumar, M.M. (2011). Composition and antioxidant activity of essential oil of pimento (*Pimenta dioica* (L) Merr.) from Jamaica. *Nat. Prod. Res.*, 25(2): 152-160.
- 51.Martinez-Velazquez, M., Castillo-Herrera, G.A., Rosario-Cruz, R., Flores-Fernandez, J.M., LopezRamirez, J., Hernandez-Gutierrez, R. and Lugo-Cervantes Edel, C. (2011). Acaricidal effect and chemical composition of essential oils extracted from *Cuminum cyminum*, *Pimenta dioica* and *Ocimum basilicum* against the cattle tick *Rhipicephalus (Boophilus) microplus* (Acari: Ixodidae). *Parasitol. Res.*, 108(2): 481-487
- 52.Filek G, Bergamini M, Lindner W. Steam distillation-solvent extraction, a selective sample enrichment technique for the gas chromatographic-electron-capture detection of organochlorine compounds in milk powder and other milk products. *Journal of Chromatography A*. 1995 Oct 13;712(2):355-64.
- 53.Lucchesi ME, Chemat F, Smadja J. An original solvent free microwave extraction of essential oils from spices. *Flavour and Fragrance Journal*. 2004 Mar;19(2):134-8.
- 54.Chan CH, Yusoff R, Ngoh GC. Optimization of microwave-assisted extraction based on absorbed microwave power and energy. *Chemical Engineering Science*. 2014 May 24;111:41-7.
- 55.Palaith D, Silberglitt R. Microwave joining of ceramics. *American Ceramic Society Bulletin* 1989;69(9):1601±1606.
- 56.Palaith D, Silberglitt R, Wu CCM, Kleiner R, Libelo EL. Microwave joining of ceramics. In: Sutton WH, Brooks MH, editors. *Microwave processing of materials*, Materials Research Society Proceedings,124. Pittsburgh: Materials Research Society, 1988. pp. 255±266.
- 57.Wei J, Delgado R, Hawley MC, DeMuse MT. Dielectric analysis of semi-crystalline poly(ethylene terephthalate). In: Iskander MF, Lauf RJ, Sutton WH, editors. *Microwave processing of materials IV*, Materials Research Society Proceedings, 347. Pittsburgh: Materials Research Society, 1994. pp. 735±741.
- 58.Metaxas AC. Applicators for industrial microwave processing. In: Clark DE, Tinga WR, Laia Jr. JR, editors. *Microwaves: theory and application in materials processing II*, ceramic transactions, Proceedings of the symposium held during the 95th Annual Meeting of the American Ceramic Society, Cincinnati, 36. Westerville, OH: The American Ceramic Society, 1993. pp. 549±562.
- 59.Janey MA, Calhoun CL, Kimrey HD. Microwave sintering of solid oxide fuel cell materials I: zirconia±8 mol% Ytria. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* 1992;75(2):314±346.
- 60.Bilal, A.; Jahan, N.; Ahmed, A.; Bilal, S. N.; Habib, S.; Hajra, S. Phytochemical and Pharmacological Studies on *Ocimum Basilicum* Linn-A Review. *Int J Curr Res Rev*. 2012, 4(23), 73–83.

61. Umamageswari, A.; Kudagi, B. Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic Properties of *Ocimum Sanctum*: A Comparative Study Using Animal Models. *Int J Basic Clin Pharmacol*. 2015, 4(5), 981–986.
62. Adam, Z. A.; Omer, A. A. Antibacterial Activity of *Ocimum Basilicum* (Rehan) Leaf Extract against Bacterial Pathogens in Sudan. *Am. J. Res. Commun*. 2015, 3(8), 94–99.
63. Al Abbasy, D. W.; Pathare, N.; Al-Sabahi, J. N.; Khan, S. A. Chemical Composition and Antibacterial Activity of Essential Oil Isolated from Omani Basil (*Ocimum Basilicum* Linn.). *Asian Pacific J Trop Dis*. 2015, 5(8), 645–649
64. Joshi, R. K.;. Chemical Composition and Antimicrobial Activity of the Essential Oil of *Ocimum Basilicum* L. (sweet Basil) from Western Ghats of North West Karnataka, India. *Ancient Sci. Life*. 2014, 33(3), 151–156.
65. Rubab, S.; Hussain, I.; Khan, B. A.; Unar, A. A.; Abbas, K. A.; Khich, Z. H.; Khan, M.; Khanum, S.; Khan, K. U.H. Biomedical Description of *Ocimum Basilicum* L. *J Islamic Int Med Colleg*. 2017, 12, 59–67.
66. Opalchenova, G.; Obreshkova, D. Comparative Studies on the Activity of Basil-an Essential Oil from *Ocimum Basilicum* L.-against Multidrug Resistant Clinical Isolates of the Genera *Staphylococcus*, *Enterococcus* and *Pseudomonas* by Using Different Test Methods. *J Microbiol Meth*. 2003, 54, 105–110.
67. Zhou L, Zheng H, Tang Y, Yu W, Gong Q. Eugenol inhibits quorum sensing at sub-inhibitory concentrations. *Biotechnol Lett* 2013;35:631-7.
68. Pei RS, Zhou F, Ji BP, Xu J. Evaluation of combined antibacterial effects of eugenol, cinnamaldehyde, thymol, and carvacrol against *E. coli* with an improved method. *J Food Sci* 2009;74:M379-83.
69. Miladi H, Zmantar T, Kouidhi B, Chaabouni Y, Mahdouani K, Bakhrouf A, et al. Use of carvacrol, thymol, and eugenol for biofilm eradication and resistance modifying susceptibility of *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhimurium strains to nalidixic acid. *Microb Pathog* 2017;104:56-63.
70. Santiesteban-López A, Palou E, López-Malo A. Susceptibility of food-borne bacteria to binary combinations of antimicrobials at selected a(w) and pH. *J Appl Microbiol* 2007;102:486-97.
71. Lewis RE. Current concepts in antifungal pharmacology. *Mayo Clin Proc* 2011;86:805-17.
72. Oxenham, S. K.; Svoboda, K. P.; Walter, D. R. Antifungal Activity of the Essential Oil of Basil (*Ocimum Basilicum*). *J. Phytopathol*. 2005, 153(3), 174–180.
73. Ahmad, K.; Khalil, A. T.; Somayya, R. Antifungal, Phytotoxic and Hemagglutination Activity of Methanolic Extracts of *Ocimum Basilicum*. *J Tradit Chin Med*. 2016, 36(6), 794–798.
74. Elsherbiny, E. A.; Safwat, N. A.; Elaasser, M. M. Fungitoxicity of Organic Extracts of *Ocimum Basilicum* on Growth and Morphogenesis of *Bipolaris* Species (Teleomorph *Cochliobolus*). *J. Appl. Microbiol*. 2017, 123(4), 841–852.
75. Gucwa, K.; Milewski, S.; Dymerski, T.; Szweda, P. Investigation of the Antifungal Activity and Mode of Action of *Thymus Vulgaris*, *Citrus Limonum*, *Pelargonium Graveolens*, *Cinnamomum Cassia*, *Ocimum Basilicum*, and *Eugenia Caryophyllus* Essential Oils. *Molecules*. 2018, 23(5). DOI: 10.3390/molecules23051116.. pii: E1116.

76. Cardoso, N. N.; Alviano, C. S.; Blank, A. F.; Arrigoni-Blank, M. F.; Romanos, M. T.; Cunha, M. M.; Da Silva, A. J.; Alviano, D. S. Anti-cryptococcal Activity of Ethanol Crude Extract and Hexane Fraction from *Ocimum Basilicum* Var. Maria Bonita: Mechanisms of Action and Synergism with Amphotericin B and *Ocimum Basilicum* Essential Oil. *Pharm. Biol.* 2017, 55(1), 1380–1388. DOI: 10.1080/13880209.2017.1302483.
77. Dasgupta, T.; Rao, A. R.; Yadava, P. K. Chemomodulatory Efficacy of Basil Leaf (*Ocimum Basilicum*) on Drug Metabolizing and Antioxidant Enzymes, and on Carcinogen-induced Skin and Forestomach Papillomagenesis. *Phytomedicine.* 2004, 11(2–3), 139–151. DOI: 10.1078/0944-7113-00289.
78. Pedro, A. C.; Moreira, F.; Granato, D.; Rosso, N. D. Extraction of Bioactive Compounds and Free Radical Scavenging Activity of Purple Basil (*Ocimum Basilicum* L.) Leaf Extracts as Affected by Temperature and Time. *Anais Da Academia Brasileira De Ciências.* 2016, 88(2), 1055–1068. DOI: 10.1590/0001-3765201620150197.
79. Tarchoune, I.; Sgherri, C.; Izzo, R.; Lachaâl, M.; Navari-Izzo, F.; Ouerghi, Z. Changes in the Antioxidative systems of *Ocimum Basilicum* L. (Cv. Fine) under Different Sodium Salts. *Acta Physiologiae Plantarum.* 2012, 34(5), 1873–1881. DOI: 10.1007/s11738-012-0985-z.
80. Tarchoune, I.; Sgherri, C.; Izzo, R.; Lachaal, M.; Ouerghi, Z.; Navari-Izzo, F. Antioxidative Responses of *Ocimum Basilicum* to Sodium Chloride or Sodium Sulphate Salinization. *Plant Physiol Biochem.* 2010, 48, 772–777
81. El-Beshbishy, H. A.; Bahashwan, S. A. Hypoglycemic Effect Of Basil (*Ocimum basilicum*) aqueous extract is mediated through inhibition of α -glucosidase and α -amylase activities. *Toxicology and Industrial Health.* 2012, 28 (1), 42–50. DOI: 10.1177/0748233711403193.
82. Horcajada, M.-N.; Offord, E. Naturally Plant-derived Compounds: Role in Bone Anabolism. . *Current Molecular Pharmacology.* 2012, 5(2), 205–218. DOI: 10.2174/1874467211205020205.
83. Bandyopadhyay, S.; Lion, J.-M.; Mentaverri, R.; Ricupero, D. A.; Kamel, S.; Romero, J. R.; Chattopadhyay, N. Attenuation of Osteoclastogenesis and Osteoclast Function by Apigenin. *Biochem Pharmacol.* 2006, 72(2), 184–197.
84. Rasheed, W. I.; Oraby, F. S.; Hussein, J. S. Therapeutic Efficacy of Garlic Oil with 1, 25 Dihydroxy Vit D and Calcium in Osteoporotic Ovariectomized Rats. *Aust J Basic Appl Sci.* 2009, 3, 977–981.
85. Harnafi, H.; Serghini, C. H.; Bouanani, N. H.; Aziz, M.; Amrani, S. Hypolipemic Activity of Polyphenol-rich Extracts from *Ocimum Basilicum* in Triton WR-1339-induced Hyperlipidemic Mice. *Food Chem.* 2008, 108, 205–212.
86. Karthikeyan, P. Gunasekaran, N. Ramamurthy and S. Govindasamy Anticancer Activity of *Ocimum Sanctum*. *Summary Pharmaceutical Biology* 1999, Vol. 37, No. 4, Pages 285-290 .
87. Kath R K & Gupta R K. Antioxidant activity of hydroalcoholic leaf extract of *Ocimum sanctum* in animal models of peptic ulcer. *Indian J Physiol Pharmacol* 2006, 50 (4): 391–396.
88. Kochhar A, Sharma N and Sachdeva R. Effect of Supplementation of Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) and Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) Leaf Powder on Diabetic Symptoms, Anthropometric Parameters and Blood Pressure of Non Insulin Dependent Male Diabetics. *Ethno-Med* 2009, 3(1): 5-9
89. Madhuri Sharma and Pandey Govind. Ethnomedicinal plants for prevention and treatment of tumours 2009, 3 (1):2-5.

90. Misra P ?, Pal NL, Guru P K, Katiyar J C and Tandon J S. Antimalarial Activity of Traditional Plants against Erythrocytic Stages of Plasmodium berghei. *Pharmaceutical Biol.* Vol. 29(1): 19-23, 1991.
91. Mandal S, Das D N, Kamala D, Ray K, Roy G, Chaudhari SB, Sahana. *Ocimum sanctum* Linn - A study on gastric ulceration and gastric secretion in rats. *Indian J Physiol Pharmacol* 1993, 37: 91– 92
92. Nagarajun S, Jain HC, Aulakh GS. Indigenous plants used in the control of Diabetes. In: *Cultivation and utilization of medicinal plants*. Editors: Atal CK and Kapoor BM (Published PID CSJR).p. 584, 1989.
93. Nair V D, Jaleel CA, Gopi R, Gomathinayagam M, Panneerselvam R. Antioxidant potential of *Ocimum sanctum* under growth regulator treatments. *EurAsia J BioSci* 2009; 3: 1- 9.
94. Akhtar, M. S.; Munir, M. Evaluation of the Gastric Antiulcerogenic Effects of *Solanum nigrum*, *Brassica Oleracea* and *Ocimum Basilicum* in Rats. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 1989, 27(1–2), 163–176.
95. Das, P.; Sahoo, S.; Sethi, R. Phytochemical and Pharmacological Investigation of the Plant *Ocimum Basilicum* with Special Reference to Its Anti-ulceration Property. *J. Pharm. Res.* 2010, 3(1), 63–66.
96. Purushothaman, B.; Srinivasan, P.; Suganthi, R.; Ranganathan, P.; Gimbut, B.; Shanmugam, K. A Comprehensive Review on *Ocimum Basilicum*. *J Nat Remedies.* 2018, 18, 71–85.
97. Rashidian, A.; Roohi, P.; Mehrzadi, S.; Ghannadi, A. R.; Minaiyan, M. Protective Effect of *Ocimum Basilicum* Essential Oil against Acetic Acid-induced Colitis in Rats. *J Evid Based Comp Altern Med.* 2015, 21, 36–42.
98. Abd El-Ghffar, E. A.; Al-Sayed, E.; Shehata, S. M.; Eldahshan, O. A.; Efferth, T. The Protective Role of *Ocimum Basilicum* L. (Basil) against Aspirin-induced Gastric Ulcer in Mice: Impact on Oxidative Stress, Inflammation, Motor Deficits and Anxiety-like Behavior. *Food Funct.* 2018, 9(8), 4457– 4468.
99. Godhwani S, Godhwani JL, Vyas DS. *Ocimum sanctum*: an experimental study evaluating its antiinflammatory, analgesic and antipyretic activity in animals. *J Ethnopharmacol* 21(2):1987,153163.
100. Singh S, Majumdar DK. Evaluation of antiinflammatory activity of fatty acids of *Ocimum sanctum* fixed oil. *Indian J Exp Biol* 35:1997,380-383